

**UZBEKISTAN SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP
SUBJECTS OF EXPORT DEVELOPMENT COMPETENCE**

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Abstract: In this article, an attempt is made to highlight the reasons and new aspects of the growing importance of improving the system of supporting the positive impact of exports on economic growth in our country.

Key words: foreign economic activity, market conditions, export, export capacity, economic growth, systematic problems of export share growth.

In the development of the country's foreign trade relations, further increasing the export potential of small business and private entrepreneurship entities, and sharply increasing the share of this sector in the foreign trade turnover play an important role. In order to achieve this goal, small business and private business entities should increase the production of modern, competitive products in foreign markets and create the necessary conditions for their export, provide legal, financial and organizational assistance, protect the exporting entrepreneurs of our country from the risks of changes in the foreign market. It is necessary to increase attention to the issues of ensuring reliable protection. In recent years, constant attention has been paid to the state's support and encouragement of export activities of business entities.

In particular, the Export Promotion Agency was established under the Ministry of Investments and Foreign Trade of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and mechanisms for providing financial assistance to exporting enterprises were created to increase the volume of exports. In the conditions of intensifying competition in world markets, it is necessary to expand the state support to exporters in order to enter new markets and strengthen their position in traditional markets by increasing the volume of product exports. In the socio-economic development prospects of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, the directions for supporting the positive effect of effective export on economic growth have been established.

In recent years, it is appropriate to develop a new system aimed at encouraging small businesses to make innovations, to fully use their opportunities in the development of small businesses in our country. Focusing on stability in this type of reform programs lays the ground for achieving macroeconomic stability through the development of small innovative business in our country.

It is worth noting that there are a number of systemic and private problems faced by local enterprises in the process of export. The problems are mainly related to exporters' difficulties in obtaining credit resources, lack of appropriate engineering infrastructure in places, obtaining necessary export permits, solving issues in the tax field, returning previously paid value added tax amounts, finding foreign clients and other aspects.

The main task of today is to further increase the country's export potential, to change the composition of the country's exports in terms of quality and quantity through the development of small business enterprises that produce products that meet the requirements of the world market, and to encourage the production and sale of products with high added value abroad. we consider that

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that in order to improve the conditions for the further development of small business and private entrepreneurship, it is necessary to implement the following:

- to further simplify and expand the mechanism of allocating preferential loans to small business and private entrepreneurial enterprises. As a result, it will be possible to attract funds for the development of production;
- further reduction of the tax burden of small business and private business enterprises. As a result, conditions will be created to direct the funds that are saved and remain at the company's disposal to new technologies.

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